

QSPR with TAU indices. Part-5. Liquid heat capacity of diverse functional organic compounds

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Abstract : Liquid heat capacity of a large data set ($n = 871$) of diverse functional compounds has been correlated with TAU indices to unravel the diagnostic feature of the TAU scheme. The data set was divided into two subsets of 436 and 435 compounds and the best model derived from each set was used to predict the property of compounds of the other set. It was found that the TAU relations could satisfactorily predict the variances of liquid heat capacity for both the sets (predictive r^2 values being 0.963 and 0.964 for sets 1 and 2 respectively). Moreover, specific contributions of functionality, branching, shape and size factors to the property could be found out from the relations. In general, the liquid heat capacity increases with increase in molecular bulk and decreases with increase in branching and functionality. Furthermore, the presence of cyclicity, halogen atoms and aromaticity has negative contributions while the presence of hydrogen bond donor group has positive contribution to the liquid heat capacity. However, it appears that TAU formalism does not adequately consider the features like cyclicity, halogen atoms, aromaticity and hydrogen bonding property as indicator variables were required to improve the final relations and thus there is enough scope for further development of the scheme considering these features.

Keywords : TAU indices, heat capacity of liquids.

Topological descriptors are mathematical entities encoding molecular graphs composed of vertices (corresponding to the atoms) and edges (representing the bonds among the atoms)¹. These are two-dimensional descriptors which take into account the internal atomic arrangement of compounds, and which encode in numerical form information about molecular size, shape, branching, presence of heteroatoms and multiple bonds². Though topological descriptors have been regularly criticized in the QSAR literature, they have proved their usefulness in numerous quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) and quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) studies¹. In the last fifty years several hundred topological indices have been introduced and also new topological indices are continuously proposed, as well as novel strategies in their search and development². The first generation topological indices include Wiener, Gordon-Scantlebury, Hosoya, Zagreb, Centric and Schultz indices³. The molecular connectivity index of Randic and higher order molecular connectivity indices of Kier and Hall, information-theoretic indices, average distance-based connectivity index, electrotopological state atom index etc. fall into the class of second generation

topological indices⁴. The third generation topological indices include triplet local vertex invariants, information indices based on distribution of distance sums, descriptors derived from the Detour matrix etc.⁵.

The main advantage of topological indices in QSAR studies is that these do not require any experimentally derived measurement and it is possible to develop a model without a previous knowledge of the receptor structure or mechanism of action of the drugs². Topological descriptors can be calculated for compounds with very different structures, and theoretical models can be built on databases without a common parent structure. As information is obtained from 2-dimensional graph, there is no alignment and conformation problem as associated with 3D-QSAR. However, physicochemical interpretation of topological indices is often difficult. Most of the topological indices are inter-correlated and there may be chance effects when a large number of topological descriptors are used in an analysis. According to Estrada⁶, it is desired to have as many molecular descriptors as possible at our disposition, but is preferred to include as few of them as possible in the QSPR and QSAR models to be developed.

Table 1. Relations of liquid heat capacity (*H*) of diverse functional compounds [set 1 (eqs. 10–17) and set 2 (eqs. 18–25)] with TAU indices

Model equation, $H = \sum \beta_i x_i + \alpha$

Eq. no.	Regression coefficients									Statistics			
	β_1 (s.e.)	β_2 (s.e.)	β_3 (s.e.)	β_4 (s.e.)	β_5 (s.e.)	β_6 (s.e.)	β_7 (s.e.)	β_8 (s.e.)	α (s.e.)	R^2 R_a^2	R (s)	F (p)	Q^2 (PRESS)
10	32.694 <i>T</i> (1.323)								186.866 (4.243)	0.585 (0.584)	0.765 (70.525)	611.0 (<0.0000)	0.580 (2184785)
11	57.751 <i>T_R</i> (0.921)	-6.379 <i>F</i> (0.946)							30.781 (4.612)	0.903 (0.903)	0.950 (34.056)	2024.2 (<0.0000)	0.902 (510932)
12	28.849 <i>N_V</i> (0.460)	-6.145 <i>F</i> (0.944)	-48.669 <i>B</i> (9.282)						24.444 (4.956)	0.904 (0.903)	0.951 (33.967)	1357.6 (<0.0000)	0.902 (510745)
13	29.804 <i>N_V</i> (0.409)	-5.928 <i>F</i> (0.824)	-17.449 <i>N_X</i> (3.353)	-16.384 <i>N_Y</i> (1.303)					27.862 (4.265)	0.927 (0.926)	0.963 (29.653)	1369.9 (<0.0000)	0.921 (409689)
14	30.097 <i>N_V</i> (0.388)	-5.563 <i>F</i> (0.780)	-20.878 <i>N_B</i> (1.342)						28.971 (4.017)	0.935 (0.934)	0.967 (28.046)	2058.5 (<0.0000)	0.933 (346664)
15	31.155 <i>N_V</i> (0.301)	-2.707 <i>F</i> (0.782)	-13.299 <i>N_X</i> (2.770)	-9.079 <i>N_Y</i> (0.974)	-39.684 <i>I_C</i> (5.417)	-5.429 <i>I_H</i> (1.422)	31.126 <i>I_{HD}</i> (2.943)	-11.981 <i>I_A</i> (5.849)	10.437 (3.069)	0.966 (0.965)	0.983 (20.377)	1511.2 (<0.0000)	0.963 (194025)
16	31.181 <i>N_V</i> (0.299)	-3.249 <i>F</i> (0.756)	-9.433 <i>N_P</i> (0.923)		-57.753 <i>I_C</i> (5.631)	-3.799 <i>I_H</i> (1.292)	31.577 <i>I_{HD}</i> (2.932)	-14.010 <i>I_A</i> (5.802)	30.473 (4.017)	0.966 (0.965)	0.983 (20.338)	1733.8 (<0.0000)	0.964 (185228)
17	31.145 <i>N_V</i> (0.305)	-3.268 <i>F</i> (0.776)	-59.353 <i>B</i> (6.446)		-46.271 <i>I_C</i> (5.526)	-3.219 <i>I_H</i> (1.362)	33.512 <i>I_{HD}</i> (2.993)	-17.496 <i>I_A</i> (5.888)	9.998 (3.125)	0.965 (0.964)	0.982 (20.726)	1667.4 (<0.0000)	0.963 (193408)
18	33.505 <i>T</i> (1.376)								181.742 (4.335)	0.578 (0.577)	0.760 (69.998)	593.1 (<0.0000)	0.573 (2147769)
19	57.154 <i>T_R</i> (0.884)	-7.107 <i>F</i> (0.931)							32.830 (4.304)	0.907 (0.907)	0.952 (32.856)	2112.6 (<0.0000)	0.906 (473787)
20	28.580 <i>N_V</i> (0.452)	-7.291 <i>F</i> (0.946)	-41.582 <i>B</i> (8.492)						26.449 (4.737)	0.905 (0.904)	0.951 (33.359)	1362.3 (<0.0000)	0.903 (490227)
21	29.854 <i>N_V</i> (0.386)	-6.439 <i>F</i> (0.790)	-22.003 <i>N_X</i> (3.010)	-18.668 <i>N_Y</i> (1.314)					30.554 (3.868)	0.934 (0.933)	0.966 (27.830)	1515.3 (<0.0000)	0.932 (342023)
22	29.873 <i>N_V</i> (0.383)	-6.378 <i>F</i> (0.785)	-19.101 <i>N_B</i> (1.257)						30.325 (3.834)	0.934 (0.934)	0.967 (27.663)	2046.3 (<0.0000)	0.933 (336689)
23	30.889 <i>N_V</i> (0.302)	-4.376 <i>F</i> (0.744)	-18.908 <i>N_X</i> (2.541)	-11.760 <i>N_Y</i> (1.043)	-42.707 <i>I_C</i> (2.640)	-3.476 <i>I_H</i> (1.288)	28.852 <i>I_{HD}</i> (2.948)		17.188 (2.967)	0.965 (0.964)	0.982 (20.358)	1671.9 (<0.0000)	0.963 (187075)
24	30.731 <i>N_V</i> (0.314)	-4.592 <i>F</i> (0.769)	-9.527 <i>N_P</i> (0.927)		-64.647 <i>I_C</i> (2.822)	-3.311 <i>I_H</i> (1.288)	29.595 <i>I_{HD}</i> (3.082)		35.974 (3.989)	0.961 (0.961)	0.980 (21.302)	1775.1 (<0.0000)	0.960 (203639)
25	30.444 <i>N_V</i> (0.322)	-4.705 <i>F</i> (0.808)	-53.993 <i>B</i> (6.448)		-56.138 <i>I_C</i> (2.674)	-3.353 <i>I_H</i> (1.371)	29.976 <i>I_{HD}</i> (3.189)		16.941 (3.268)	0.959 (0.958)	0.979 (22.048)	1652.4 (<0.0000)	0.956 (219292)

Though topological indices have long been used successfully for modeling biological activity and physico-chemical properties, the recent years have witnessed an upsurge in the interest of developing new graph theoretical descriptors, in view of new applications of such descriptors in similarity and diversity assessment, database mining and virtual assessment of combinatorial library and pattern recognition⁷.

Materials and methods :

The definitions of different TAU parameters are listed below⁸.

The first order composite index T : The first order composite topochemical index (*T*) is defined as

$$T = \sum_{i < j} E_{ij} = \sum_{i < j} (V_i V_j)^{0.5} \tag{1}$$

where E_{ij} represents the VEM edge weight of the edge between *i*-th and *j*-th vertices and V_i is the VEM vertex weight of the *i*-th vertex, V_i is defined as

$$V_i = \lambda_i / \theta_i \tag{2}$$

$$\lambda_i = \text{Core count of the } i\text{-th vertex} = (Z - Z^y) / Z^y \tag{3}$$

$$\theta_i = \text{VEM count of the } i\text{-th vertex}$$

$$= 8 - (2h + 1.5v + n), \text{ when unsaturation is not present} \tag{4}$$

$$= 0.5v + 2\pi, \text{ when unsaturation is present} \tag{5}$$

h = number of hydrogen atom(s) suppressed at the atom

v = number of sigma bonds (other than hydrogen) attached

to the atom

n = number of nonbonded electrons attached to the atom

π = number of pi bonds associated with the atom.

In case of a heteroatom, the VEM edge weight of an edge incident upon the heteroatom is given a negative value (i.e. multiplied by -1).

Fig. 1. Scatter plots of observed versus predicted liquid heat capacity values for (a) set 1 compounds; (b) set 2 compounds

The functionality index F : The composite index T can further be divided into two components : skeletal index T_R and functionality F . The skeletal index T_R is the topochemical index of the reference alkane that may be obtained by replacing heteroatom with carbon and removing the multiple bonds that may be present. Again, functionality F is defined as

$$F = T_R - T \quad (6)$$

The first order VEM skeletal index T_R is considered as the index for intrinsic lipophilicity.

The branching index B : The skeletal index T_R is further partitioned to derive branching index B .

$$B = T_N - T_R \quad (7)$$

T_N is the topochemical index of the corresponding normal alkane.

Simplest topological integers from molecular structures (STIMS) :

The vertex count N_V of the reference alkane may further be partitioned into N_P (number of methyl carbons), N_I (number of methylene carbons), N_B (number of branched carbons). N_B is composed of N_Y (number of tertiary carbons) and N_X (number of quaternary carbons). Thus, obviously,

$$N_V = N_P + N_I + N_X + N_Y \quad (8)$$

The vertex count (N_V) of the hydrogen-suppressed molecular formula is purely a constitutional parameter because it may be obtained directly from the molecular formula. Even structural formula is not needed for obtaining the value of N_V . Obviously, any index showing better correlation with physicochemical or biological activity than that shown by N_V will have significance in the context of QSPR/QSAR studies. N_V may be considered as the molecular bulk parameter whereas N_B , N_P , N_X and N_Y represent shape parameters.

All TAU indices are basically derived by sequentially partitioning the first order composite index T into different components. During development of QSAR equations with TAU parameters, above-mentioned hierarchical relations are followed. For obvious reasons, B and N_B , or N_P and N_B , or N_V and N_I are not used in the same equation⁸.

The data set : The liquid heat capacity values of diverse functional compounds ($n = 871$) were taken from the literature⁹. The data set includes all sorts of organic compounds. The present paper attempts to compare the quality of the TAU relations with the relations derived from other diverse descriptors in order to explore any lacunae present in the TAU formalism. The data set was divided into two subsets (subset 1, $n = 436$, odd serial numbers; subset 2, $n = 435$, even serial numbers) each of which was used as the training set to derive equations for prediction of liquid heat capacity of the other (test) set^ψ.

Statistical analysis : Multiple linear regression analyses were done using the package MINITAB¹⁰. The statistical quality of the equations¹¹ was assessed by examining the parameters like Q^2 (crossvalidation R^2 or predicted variance using leave-one-out method), R_a^2 (adjusted R^2 , i.e. explained variance), r or R (correlation coefficient), F (variance ratio) with df (degree of freedom), S (standard error of estimate) and $PRESS$ (predicted residual sum of squares). Significance of the regression coefficients was assessed

^ψThose who are interested in the list of compounds and their heat capacity values, may contact authors.

by the 'r' test. The quality of prediction in case of external validation was expressed as predictive r^2 (r_{pred}^2), which is defined as follows :

$$r_{\text{pred}}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (Y_{\text{obs}} - Y_{\text{pred}})^2}{\sum (Y_{\text{obs}} - \bar{Y})^2} \quad (9)$$

In the above equation, Y_{obs} and Y_{pred} indicate observed and predicted property values respectively and \bar{Y} indicate mean property value of the corresponding training set.

Results and discussion

The relations of liquid heat capacity of set 1 compounds (eqs. (10)–(17)) with TAU indices are presented in Table 1. The first order composite topochemical index T could explain 58.4% of the variance while the predicted variance value was 58.0% (eq. (10)). When the composite index was partitioned into the first order skeletal index T_R and functionality index F (eq. (11)), the explained variance and predicted variance values rose to 90.3 and 90.2% respectively. The intrinsic lipophilicity (T_R) shows a positive contribution while the functionality F shows a negative contribution to the liquid heat capacity as evident from the regression coefficients of eq. (11). The skeletal index T_R was further partitioned into the bulk parameter vertex count (N_V) and branching B , and the resulted eq. (12) was comparable in statistical quality to that of eq. (11). The positive coefficient of N_V indicates that the liquid heat capacity increases with increase in size and the negative coefficient of B indicates that the response parameter decreases as branching increases. When shape indices N_X and N_Y were used instead of B (eq. (13)), there was considerable rise in statistical quality ($R_a^2 = 0.926$, $Q^2 = 0.921$). The coefficients of N_X and N_Y indicate that tertiary and quaternary branching have almost equal and negative contributions to the liquid heat capacity. When N_B was used instead of N_X and N_Y (eq. (14)), there was further rise in statistical quality ($R_a^2 = 0.934$, $Q^2 = 0.933$). In order to further improve the statistical quality, indicator variables like I_C , I_H , I_{HD} and I_A (indicating presence or absence of cyclicity, halogen atoms, hydrogen bond donor group and aromaticity respectively) were tried and eqs. (15)–(17) were obtained. It is observed that on using the indicator parameters, statistical quality is further enhanced (up to 96.4% predicted variance). Furthermore, presence of cyclicity, halogen atoms and aromaticity has negative contribution while presence of hydrogen bond donor group has positive contribution to the liquid heat capacity. The negative coefficient of N_p in eq. (16) indicates negative contribution of the branching.

The relations of liquid heat capacity of set 2 compounds

(eqs. (18)–(25)) with TAU indices are also presented in Table 1, which show comparable relations as found in case of set 1 compounds. The composite topochemical index T could explain and predict 57.7% and 57.3% respectively of the variance of liquid heat capacity (eq. (18)). On partitioning the composite index into T_R and F (eq. (19)), explained and predicted variance values increased to 90.7% and 90.6% respectively. The skeletal index T_R shows positive contribution while functionality F shows negative contribution. When T_R was further factored into N_V and B (eq. (20)), almost comparable relation with positive contribution of bulk (N_V) and negative contribution of branching (B) was obtained. When the shape parameters N_X and N_Y were used instead of B (eq. (21)), considerable rise in statistical quality was obtained ($R_a^2 = 0.933$, $Q^2 = 0.932$). When N_X and N_Y were substituted with N_B (eq. (22)), the statistical quality remained same ($R_a^2 = 0.934$, $Q^2 = 0.933$). In order to further improve the statistical quality, indicator variables like I_C , I_H and I_{HD} (indicating presence or absence of cyclicity, halogen atoms and hydrogen bond donor group) were tried and eqs. (23)–(25) were obtained. It is observed that on using the indicator parameters, statistical quality was further enhanced (upto 96.3% predicted variance). Furthermore, presence of cyclicity and halogen atoms has negative contribution while presence of hydrogen bond donor group has positive contribution to the liquid heat capacity. The negative coefficient of N_p in eq. (24) indicates negative contribution of the branching.

Eq. (15) obtained from set 1 compounds was also used to predict liquid heat capacity of set 2 compounds and predictive r^2 values was found to be 0.963. Similarly, eq. (23) obtained from set 2 compounds was applied to predict liquid heat capacity of set 1 compounds and predictive r^2 value was found to be 0.964. The scatter plots of observed versus predicted liquid heat capacity of two sets of compounds are given in Fig. 1. The statistical quality of the best models for the two sets is comparable to that of the MLR equation ($R = 0.986$) reported previously⁹. TAU indices could decode specific contributions of molecular bulk (size), functionality, branching and shape parameters to the liquid heat capacity of diverse functional compounds. In general, the liquid heat capacity increases with increase in bulk and decreases with increase in branching. Furthermore, the liquid heat capacity is negatively contributed by the functionality. However, it is clear that we had to use indicator parameters to improve the statistical quality of the models. The presence of cyclicity, halogen atoms and aromaticity have negative contributions while the presence of hydrogen bond donor group has positive contribution to the

liquid heat capacity. It appears that TAU formalism does not adequately consider the features like cyclicality, halogen atoms, aromaticity and hydrogen bonding property and thus there is enough scope for further development considering these features. We may mention here that to refine the TAU scheme and fill the lacunae present in the formalism, extended topochemical atom (ETA) indices have been recently introduced and applied in toxicity modeling¹². In future, ETA indices will also be applied in property modeling to prove their potential in modeling studies.

References

1. J. Devillers, in "Topological Indices and Related Descriptors in QSAR and QSPR", eds. J. Devillers and A. T. Balaban, Gordon and Breach, Amsterdam, 1999, pp. 1-20.
2. R. Gozalbes, J. P. Doucet and F. Derouin, *Current Drug Targets-Infectious Disorders*, 2002, **2**, 93.
3. H. Wiener, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 17; M. Gordon and G. R. Scantlebury, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 604; H. Hosoya, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **44**, 2332; I. Gutman, B. Ruscic, N. Trinajstić and C. F. Wilcox, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, **62**, 3399; A. T. Balaban, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1979, **5**, 239; H. P. Schultz, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1989, **29**, 227.
4. M. Randić, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 6609; L. B. Kier and L. H. Hall, "Molecular Connectivity in Chemistry and Drug Research", Academic Press, New York, 1976; D. Bonchev, "Information Theoretic Indices for Characterization of Chemical Structure", Research Studies Press-Wiley, Chichester, 1983; A. T. Balaban, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1982, **89**, 399; L. H. Hall and L. B. Kier, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1995, **35**, 1039.
5. P. A. Filip, T. -S. Balaban and A. T. Balaban, *J. Math. Chem.*, 1987, **1**, 61; A. T. Balaban and V. Feroiu, *Rep. Mol. Theor.*, 1990, **1**, 133; O. Ivanciuc and A. T. Balaban, *MATCH (Commun. Math. Chem.)*, 1994, **30**, 141.
6. E. Estrada, in "Topological Indices and Related Descriptors in QSAR and QSPR", eds., J. Devillers and A. T. Balaban, Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, The Netherlands, 1999, pp. 403-453.
7. O. Ivanciuc, in "Encyclopedia of Computational Chemistry", eds. P. Schleyer, R. Van, N. L. Allinger, T. Clark, J. Gasteiger, P. A. Kollman, H. F. Schaefer III and P. R. Schreiner, John Wiley, Chichester, 1998, pp. 167-183; D. Bostick and I. I. Vaiman, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 2003, **304**, 320; M. Sismilich, M. I. Menzies, P. W. Gandar, P. E. Jameson and J. Clemens, *J. Theor. Biol.*, 2003, **220**, 371.
8. D. K. Pal, C. Sengupta and A. U. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 734; 1989, **28**, 261; D. K. Pal, M. Sengupta, C. Sengupta and A. U. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, **29**, 451; D. K. Pal, S. K. Purkayastha, C. Sengupta and A. U. De, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 109.
9. X. Yao, B. Fan, J. P. Doucet, A. Panaye, M. Liu, R. Zhang, X. Zhang and Z. Hu, *QSAR Comb. Sci.*, 2003, **22**, 29.
10. MINITAB is a statistical software of MINITAB Inc., USA.
11. G. W. Snedecor and W. G. Cochran, "Statistical Methods", Oxford & IBH Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1967, pp. 381-418; S. Wold and L. Eriksson in "Chemometric Methods in Molecular Design", ed. H. van de Waterbeemd, VCH, Weinheim, 1995, p. 312.
12. K. Roy and G. Ghosh, *Internet Electron. J. Mol. Des.*, 2003, **2**, 599, <http://www.biochempress.com>; *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 2004, **44**, 559; *QSAR Comb. Sci.*, 2004, **23**, 99, 526; *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **13**, 1185; *J. Mol. Model.*, 2005, **11**, in press. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00894-005-0033-7>.